

Calculation of molecular polarizability and water solubility of alkanes and alcohols

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Manuscript received 10 July 2000, accepted 8 December 2000

Molecular polarizabilities and water solubilities of alkanes and alcohols have been calculated resorting to quite simple regression equations within the framework of the Quantitative Structure Activity (Property) Relationships theory. The basic molecular descriptors are atoms and chemical bonds. Results are quite satisfactory and compare favorably with another one determined via more elaborated indices. Some possible future extensions of the method are pointed out.

The polarizability of a many-electron system is its linear response to an oscillating electric field and can be defined through the induced moment¹. The interaction of a collection of charged particles with an electric field (F) may be expressed as an interaction between the dipole moment (d) of the system by the addition of a term,

$$H^{(1)} = -dF \quad (1)$$

to the original Hamiltonian operator $H^{(0)}$, where

$$d = \sum_i e_i r_i \quad (2)$$

The field may also interact with higher multipole moments of the charge distribution insofar the spatial derivatives of the field do not disappear. The application of the Hellmann-Feynman theorem plus the Taylor series expansion about the unperturbed energy ($E^{(0)}$) gives the dependence of the energy of the system on the field, $E(F)$,

$$E(F) = E(0) - \mu_e \cdot F - 1/2 \alpha : FF - \dots \quad (3)$$

where,

$$d = \mu_e + \alpha \cdot F + 1/2 \beta : FF + \dots \quad (4)$$

μ_e is the permanent dipole moment vector, α the polarizability tensor and β the first hyperpolarizability tensor.

The polarizability and hyperpolarizability tensors should be viewed as proportionality constants which measure the response of the system to the applied field. According to eqn.(4) they are the constants of proportionality between the induced dipole moment and various powers of the field. Polarizability of a molecule may be calculated from perturbation theory. In fact, using $H^{(1)}$ as a perturbation, general perturbation formulae are

$$\begin{aligned} E(F) &= E(0) + \sum \lambda_q^{(1)} F_q + \sum \lambda_{qq}^{(2)} F_q F_{q'} + \dots \\ &\equiv E(0) + \lambda^{(1)} F + \lambda^{(2)} : FF + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and then we identify $\lambda^{(i)}$ with the tensors we require. This perturbation expansion allows us to derive other physically important quantities, such as the polarization of the medium (P), the susceptibility of the medium (χ_e), the dielectric constant or relative permittivity (K_e) and the refractive index (n_r) of the medium².

Electronic structure computations are widely employed in understanding and design of molecules exhibiting linear or nonlinear optical responses³. For designed refractive index materials, the fundamental molecular response property is the frequency-dependent polarizability $\alpha(\omega)$ and this tensor may be calculated through *ab initio* calculations⁴.

A quite natural question concerns the possible additive properties of α for a molecule. Since polarizability has the dimension of volume and it has been found that molecular polarizabilities are approximately additive, the answer seems to be positive. In fact, for halogenated benzenes with one, two, three, four, five, or six halogen substituents, it has been found that the individual tensor elements α_{zz} , $1/2(\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy})$ and $1/2(\alpha_{xx} - \alpha_{yy})$ are indeed additive and it could be demonstrated that polarizabilities of aromatic molecules can be described through the additivity of atomic polarizability tensors⁵. Furthermore, the description of the molecular polarizability by additive atomic or group polarizabilities is an old and well-established concept⁶ and recently it has also been employed in some detail⁷.

Of late, Zhu and Jiang⁸ have also shown the direct relationship between the increasing of the polarizabilities for the substituted cumulenes of the SCH₃-CHO pair and the corresponding polyenes with the increment of conjugated carbon atoms between the donor and acceptor groups. Doeksen and Thakkar⁹ have recently resorted to additive atom model of polarizability for five- and six-membered rings containing B, C, N, and O atoms and also applied a

purely additive connections models to express the polarizability as a linear combination of the number of connections (i.e. bonds without regard to bond orders).

Thus, we have deemed interesting to look for a general way to correlate molecular polarizability with the number and sort of atoms constituting molecules with the aim to try to find simple enough mathematical relationships to compute this physical chemistry property. This paper is organized as follows : next section deals with the method and the chosen molecular sets to determine the multilinear regression relationships. Then, we present the results, comparing them with other theoretical values and available experimental data. We discuss the results, trying to analyze their potential uses for other molecular sets and/or other physical chemistry properties. Finally, we state the main conclusions as well as the relative merits of the present approach.

Method :

Molecular polarizability is a feature property related to molecular structure. Then, it can be predicted that the application of molecular indices currently used in Quantitative Structure Activity (Property) Relationships (QSAR/QSPR) will lead to satisfactory quantitative representations of molecular polarizabilities.

At present, standard literature registers a huge number of such indices and it seems rather difficult to be sure that the chosen set is the right one. Lately, we have shown that resorting to the simplest and most elementary topological indices yields good enough results in order to describe biological activities and physical chemistry properties¹⁰. These indices are the number of atoms of each kind and the number and sort of chemical bonds, so that the mathematical formula relating property (or activity) with molecular indices is

$$\text{Property} = \sum_i^{\text{atoms}} a_i n_i + \sum_{i-j}^{\text{bonds}} b_{i-j} n_{i-j} + c \quad (6)$$

where n_i is the number of the i -th atom, n_{i-j} is the number of the $i-j$ -th chemical bond and a_i , b_{i-j} and c are fitting parameters associated to each class of atoms and bonds.

Recently, Chenzhong and Zhiliang¹¹ have proposed the polarizability effect index of chemical groups and the molecular polarizability effect index on the basis of the principle that molecules are polarized by electric fields. They computed molecular polarizabilities by means of the method of additivity where the essential units are the chemical CH₃, CH₂-, CH< and -C< groups, which consist of three C-H bonds, two C-H and one C-C bonds, one C-H and two C-C bonds, and three C-C bonds, respectively. Thus, they could

obtain molecular polarizabilities for a set of 150 alkanes bearing 1 to 10 carbon atoms (MPEI) (see Table 2 in Ref. 11). These data allowed them to compute water solubilities (log S) for a set of 51 alcohols and 18 hydrocarbons. Then, our aim is to compute MPEI and log S for the same molecular set chosen in Ref. 11 on the basis of equation like eqn. (6), in order to compare results.

Results and Discussion

We have obtained the following multilinear regression equations :

$$\text{MPEI} = 1.8446 (\pm 0.1460) n(C_{\text{prim}}) + 1.4788 (\pm 0.0172) n(C_{\text{sec}}) + 1.2583 (\pm 0.1508) n(C_{\text{tert}}) + 1.1115 (\pm 0.2950) n(C_{\text{quat}}) - 1.5477 (\pm 0.3098); R^2 = 0.9879 \quad (7)$$

$$-\log S_{\text{alcohols}} = 0.8467 (\pm 0.0959) n(C_{\text{prim}}) + 0.5860 (\pm 0.0156) n(C_{\text{sec}}) + 0.1407 (\pm 0.1049) n(C_{\text{tert}}) - 0.4286 (\pm 0.2040) n(C_{\text{quat}}) - 2.6505 (\pm 0.1439); R^2 = 0.9703 \quad (8)$$

$$-\log S_{\text{alkanes}} = 0.9602 (\pm 0.1275) n(C_{\text{prim}}) + 0.5806 (\pm 0.0585) n(C_{\text{sec}}) + 0.1462 (\pm 0.1259) n(C_{\text{tert}}) - 0.4913 (\pm 0.2874) n(C_{\text{quat}}) - 0.3534 (\pm 0.4263); R^2 = 0.8950 \quad (9)$$

where $n(C_{\text{prim}})$ stands for the number of primary carbon atoms, etc.

Numerical results are displayed in Tables 1–3. We see that correlations between different theoretical values and theoretical and experimental data are quite satisfactory, with relatively low average absolute deviations. When comparing present results with those of previously published, we note that the former ones are slightly better than latter ones. In fact, data gathered in Table 1 show that our procedure is capable to reproduce quite well theoretical MPEI values, since the average deviation is 0.0751 for a wide set of hydrocarbons (150 molecules) and this error represents less than 1%. Besides, with the sole exception of the methane molecule, there are no 'pathological' deviations.

Regarding water solubilities of alcohols, average absolute deviations obtained from our method and that one previously published¹¹, are practically identical (0.14 and 0.15, respectively) for this set of 51 molecules. However, water solubilities for alkanes (18 molecules) are better described by the method based upon MPEI values than within the framework of the present approach. But, an inspection of the fifth column of Table 3 shows that there are not extreme deviations in any case. Perhaps, with a more extended molecular test set these results could change significantly in order to obtain more accurate predictions.

Although the employment of these basic molecular descriptors do not provide any physical insight into the mo-

Table 1. MPEI values of alkanes bearing 1-10 carbon atoms									
N^0	Alkane	MPEI ^a	MPEI ^b	Deviation ^c					
1	Methane	1.0000	0.2970	-0.7030	55	4,4-Dimethylheptane	12.8293	12.8577	0.0284
2	Ethane	2.2811	2.1416	-0.1395	56	3-Ethyl-3-methylhexane	12.8829	12.8577	-0.0252
3	Propane	3.6584	3.6204	-0.0380	57	3,3-Diethylpentane	12.9407	12.8577	-0.0830
4	2-Methylpropane	5.1320	5.2446	0.1126	58	2,3,4-Trimethylhexane	12.8829	12.9293	0.0464
5	Butane	5.0827	5.0992	0.0166	59	2,4-Dimethyl-3-ethylpentane	12.9019	12.9293	0.0274
6	2,2-Dimethylpropane	6.7018	6.9423	0.2405	60	2,3,5-Trimethylhexane	12.8251	12.9293	0.1042
7	2-Methylbutane	6.6033	6.7234	0.1201	61	2,3-Dimethylheptane	12.7268	12.7841	0.0573
8	Pentane	6.5346	6.5781	0.0435	62	3-Ethyl-2-methylhexane	12.7854	12.7841	-0.0013
9	2,2-Dimethylbutane	8.2201	8.4212	0.2011	63	3,4-Dimethylheptane	12.7705	12.7841	0.0136
10	2,3-Dimethylbutane	8.1709	8.3475	0.1766	64	3-Ethyl-4-methylhexane	12.8143	12.7841	-0.0302
11	2-Methylpentane	8.0828	8.2023	0.1195	65	2,4-Dimethylheptane	12.7167	12.7841	0.0674
12	3-Methylpentane	8.1022	8.2023	0.1001	66	4-Ethyl-2-methylhexane	12.7565	12.7841	0.0276
13	Hexane	8.0046	8.0570	0.0524	67	3,5-Dimethylheptane	12.7416	12.7841	0.0425
14	2,2,3-Trimethylbutane	9.8347	10.0453	0.2106	68	2,5-Dimethylheptane	12.6979	12.7841	0.0862
15	2,2-Dimethylpentane	9.7273	10.0469	0.3196	69	2,6-Dimethylheptane	12.6584	12.7841	0.1257
16	3,3-Dimethylpentane	9.7661	10.0469	0.2808	70	2-Methyloctane	12.5683	12.6388	0.0705
17	2,3-Dimethylpentane	9.6794	9.8264	0.1470	71	3-Methyloctane	12.6058	12.6388	0.0330
18	2,4-Dimethylpentane	9.6586	9.8264	0.1678	72	4-Methyloctane	12.6063	12.6388	0.0325
19	2-Methylhexane	9.5709	9.6811	0.1102	73	3-Ethylheptane	12.6581	12.6388	-0.0193
20	3-Methylhexane	9.5998	9.6811	0.0813	74	4-Ethylheptane	12.6730	12.6388	-0.0342
21	3-Ethylpentane	9.6287	9.6811	0.0524	75	Nonane	12.4794	12.4935	0.0141
22	Heptane	9.4874	9.5358	0.0484	76	2,2,3,3,4-Pentamethylpentane	14.8442	14.8460	0.0018
23	2,2,3,3-Tetramethylbutane	11.5456	11.7430	0.1974	77	2,2,3,3-Tetramethylhexane	14.7081	14.7007	0.0074
24	2,2,3-Trimethylpentane	11.3889	11.5241	0.1352	78	3-Ethyl-2,3-trimethylpentane	14.7755	14.7007	-0.0748
25	2,3,3-Trimethylpentane	11.4082	11.5241	0.1159	79	3,3,4,4-Tetramethylhexane	14.7659	14.7007	-0.0652
26	2,2,4-Trimethylpentane	11.3306	11.5241	0.1935	80	2,2,3,4,4-Pentamethylpentane	14.7858	14.8460	0.0602
27	2,2-Dimethylhexane	11.2335	11.3789	0.1454	81	2,2,3,4-Tetramethylhexane	14.6201	14.6271	0.0070
28	3,3-Dimethylhexane	11.2913	11.3789	0.0876	82	3-Ethyl-2,2,4-trimethylhexane	14.6486	14.6271	-0.0215
29	3-Ethyl-3-methylpentane	11.3396	11.3789	0.0392	83	2,3,4,4-Tetramethylhexane	14.6493	14.6271	-0.0222
30	2,3,4-Trimethylpentane	11.3202	11.4505	0.1303	84	2,2,3,5-Tetramethylhexane	14.5527	14.6271	0.0744
31	2,3-Dimethylhexane	11.2131	11.3052	0.0921	85	2,2,3-Trimethylheptane	14.4491	14.4818	0.0327
32	3-Ethyl-2-methylpentane	11.2515	11.3052	0.0537	86	2,2-Dimethyl-3-ethylhexane	14.5225	14.4818	-0.0407
33	3,4-Dimethylhexane	11.2420	11.3052	0.0632	87	3,3,4-Trimethylheptane	14.5271	14.4818	-0.0453
34	2,4-Dimethylhexane	11.1937	11.3052	0.1115	88	3,3-Dimethyl-4-ethylhexane	14.5803	14.4818	-0.0985
35	2,5-Dimethylhexane	11.1553	11.3052	0.1499	89	2,3,3,4-Tetramethylhexane	14.6684	14.6271	-0.0413
36	2-Methylheptane	11.0665	11.1599	0.0934	90	3,4,4-Trimethylheptane	14.5366	14.4818	-0.0548
37	3-Methylheptane	11.1007	11.1599	0.0592	91	3,4-Dimethyl-3-ethylhexane	14.5997	14.4818	-0.1179
38	4-Methylheptane	11.1102	11.1599	0.0497	92	3-Ethyl-2,3,4-trimethylpentane	14.7069	14.6271	-0.0798
39	3-Ethylhexane	11.1445	11.1599	0.0154	93	2,3,5-Tetramethylhexane	14.5911	14.6271	0.0360
40	Octane	10.9797	11.0147	0.0350	94	2,3,3-Trimethylpentane	14.4834	14.5241	0.0407
41	2,2,3,3-Tetramethylpentane	13.1467	13.2219	0.0751	95	2,3-Dimethyl-3-ethylhexane	14.5708	14.4818	-0.0890
42	2,2,3,4-Tetramethylpentane	13.0392	13.1482	0.1090	96	3,3-Diethyl-2-methylpentane	14.6381	14.4818	-0.1563
43	2,2,3-Trimethylhexane	12.9227	13.0030	0.0803	97	2,2,4,4-Tetramethylhexane	14.6305	14.7007	0.0702
44	2,2-Dimethyl-3-ethylpentane	12.9706	13.0030	0.0324	98	2,2,4,5-Tetramethylhexane	14.5333	14.6271	0.0938
45	3,3,4-Trimethylhexane	12.9805	13.0030	0.0225	99	2,2,4-Trimethylheptane	14.4198	14.4818	0.0620
46	2,3,3,4-Tetramethylpentane	13.0781	13.1482	0.0701	100	2,2-Dimethyl-4-ethylhexane	14.4647	14.4818	0.0171
47	2,3,3-Trimethylhexane	12.9516	13.0030	0.0514	101	3,3,5-Trimethylheptane	14.4788	14.4818	0.0030
48	2,3-Dimethyl-3-ethylpentane	13.0094	13.0030	-0.0064	102	2,4,4-Trimethylheptane	14.4633	14.4818	0.0185
49	2,2,4,4-Tetramethylpentane	13.0303	13.2219	0.1916	103	2,4-Dimethyl-4-ethylhexane	14.5244	14.4818	-0.0426
50	2,2,4-Trimethylhexane	12.8839	13.0030	0.1191	104	2,2,5,5-Tetramethylhexane	14.5346	14.7007	0.1661
51	2,4,4-Trimethylhexane	12.9128	13.0030	0.0902	105	2,2,5-Trimethylheptane	14.3913	14.4818	0.0905
52	2,2,5-Trimethylhexane	12.8360	13.0030	0.1670	106	2,5,5-Trimethylheptane	14.4256	14.4818	0.0562
53	2,2-Dimethylheptane	12.7418	12.8577	0.1159	107	2,2,6-Trimethylheptane	14.3463	14.4818	0.1355
54	3,3-Dimethylheptane	12.8103	12.8577	0.0474	108	2,2-Dimethyloctane	14.2531	14.3365	0.0834
					109	3,3-Dimethyloctane	14.3281	14.3365	0.0084
					110	4,4-Dimethyloctane	14.3578	14.3365	-0.0213

Table-1 (contd.)

111	3-Ethyl-3-methylheptane	14.4147	14.3365	-0.0782
112	4-Ethyl-4-methylheptane	14.4390	14.3365	-0.1025
113	3,3-Diethylhexane	14.5021	14.3365	-0.1656
114	2,3,4,5-Tetramethylhexane	14.5418	14.4082	-0.0116
115	2,3,4-Trimethylheptane	14.4242	14.4082	-0.0160
116	2,3-Dimethyl-4-ethylhexane	14.4732	14.4082	-0.0650
117	2,4-Dimethyl-3-ethylhexane	14.4827	14.4082	-0.0745
118	3,4,5-Trimethylheptane	14.4584	14.5534	-0.0502
119	2,4-Dimethyl-3-isopropylpentane	14.5799	14.5534	-0.0265
120	3-Isopropyl-2-methylhexane	14.4538	14.1498	-0.3040
121	2,3,5-Trimethylheptane	14.3858	14.4082	0.0224
122	2,5-Dimethyl-3-ethylhexane	14.4154	14.4082	-0.0072
123	2,4,5-Trimethylheptane	14.3953	14.4082	0.0129
124	2,3,6-Trimethylheptane	14.3367	14.4082	0.0715
125	2,3-Dimethyloctane	14.2414	14.2629	0.0215
126	3-Ethyl-2-methylheptane	14.3118	14.2629	-0.0489
127	3,4-Dimethyloctane	14.2937	14.2629	-0.0308
128	4-Isopropyloctane	14.3320	14.2629	-0.0691
129	4-Ethyl-3-methylheptane	14.3608	14.2629	-0.0979
130	4,5-Dimethyloctane	14.3085	14.2629	-0.0456
131	3-Ethyl-4-methylheptane	14.3555	14.2629	-0.0926
132	3,4-Diethylhexane	14.4046	14.2629	-0.1417
133	2,4,6-Trimethylheptane	14.3361	14.4082	0.0721
134	2,4-Dimethyloctane	14.2366	14.2629	0.0263
135	4-Ethyl-2-methylheptane	14.2975	14.2629	-0.0346
136	3,5-Dimethyloctane	14.2741	14.2629	-0.0112
137	3-Ethyl-5-methylheptane	14.3171	14.2629	-0.0542
138	2,5-Dimethyloctane	14.2273	14.2629	0.0356
139	5-Ethyl-2-methylheptane	14.2681	14.2629	-0.0052
140	3,6-Dimethyloctane	14.2500	14.2629	0.0129
141	2,6-Dimethyloctane	14.2071	14.2629	0.0558
142	2,7-Dimethyloctane	14.1663	14.2629	0.0966
143	2-Methylnonane	14.0753	14.1176	0.0423
144	3-Methylnonane	14.1149	14.1176	0.0027
145	4-Methylnonane	14.1330	14.1176	-0.0154
146	3-Ethyldecane	14.1727	14.1176	-0.0051
147	5-Methylnonane	14.1384	14.1176	-0.0208
148	4-Ethyldecane	14.1961	14.1176	-0.0785
149	4-Propylheptane	14.2143	14.1176	-0.0967
150	Decane	13.9848	13.9724	-0.0124
	Absolute average deviation ^d	-	-	0.0751

^aPresent work. ^bRef. 11. ^cDeviation = MPEI (Ref. 11) - MPEI (Present work). ^dAbsolute average deviation = $\sum_{i=1}^{150} |MPEI_i(\text{Ref.11}) - MPEI_i(\text{Present work})| / 150$;

Table 2. Water solubilities (log S) for alcohols*

N ⁰	Alcohol	-log S _{exp}	-log S _{calc} ^a	-log S _{calc} ^b
1	1-Butanol	-0.00	0.13 (0.13)	-0.05 (0.05)
2	2-Methyl-1-propanol	-0.01	-0.24 (0.23)	-0.23 (0.22)
3	2-Butanol	-0.03	-0.24 (0.21)	-0.23 (0.20)
4	1-Pentanol	0.58	0.47 (0.11)	0.54 (0.04)
5	3-Methyl-1-butanol	0.51	0.35 (0.16)	0.36 (0.15)
6	2-Methyl-1-butanol	0.46	0.32 (0.14)	0.36 (0.10)
7	2-Pentanol	0.28	0.35 (-0.07)	0.36 (-0.08)
8	3-Pentanol	0.21	0.32 (-0.11)	0.36 (-0.15)

Table-2 (contd.)

9	3-Methyl-2-butanol	0.18	0.22 (-0.04)	0.17 (0.01)
10	2-Methyl-2-butanol	-0.15	0.14 (-0.29)	0.05 (-0.20)
11	1-Hexanol	1.21	1.08 (0.13)	1.12 (0.09)
12	2-Hexanol	0.87	0.95 (-0.08)	0.94 (-0.07)
13	3-Hexanol	0.80	0.91 (-0.11)	0.94 (-0.14)
14	3-Methyl-3-pentanol	0.36	0.65 (-0.29)	0.63 (-0.27)
15	2-Methyl-2-pentanol	0.49	0.71 (-0.22)	0.63 (-0.14)
16	2-Methyl-3-pentanol	0.70	0.76 (-0.06)	0.76 (-0.06)
17	3-Methyl-2-pentanol	0.71	0.76 (-0.05)	0.76 (-0.05)
18	2,3-Dimethyl-2-butanol	0.37	0.55 (-0.18)	0.45 (-0.08)
19	3,3-Dimethyl-1-butanol	1.12	0.71 (0.41)	0.63 (0.49)
20	3,3-Dimethyl-2-butanol	0.61	0.55 (0.06)	0.45 (0.16)
21	4-Methyl-1-pentanol	0.99	0.95 (0.04)	0.94 (0.05)
22	4-Methyl-2-pentanol	0.79	0.82 (-0.03)	0.76 (0.03)
23	2-Ethyl-1-butanol	1.21	0.86 (0.35)	0.94 (0.27)
24	Cyclohexanol	0.42	0.19 (0.23)	0.42 (0.00)
25	1-Heptanol	1.81	1.68 (0.13)	1.71 (0.10)
26	2-Methyl-2-hexanol	1.07	1.29 (-0.22)	1.22 (-0.15)
27	3-Methyl-3-hexanol	0.98	1.21 (-0.23)	1.22 (-0.24)
28	3-Ethyl-3-pentanol	0.83	1.13 (-0.30)	1.22 (-0.39)
29	2,3-Dimethyl-2-pentanol	0.87	1.06 (-0.19)	1.03 (-0.16)
30	2,3-Dimethyl-3-pentanol	0.84	1.03 (-0.19)	1.03 (-0.19)
31	2,4-Dimethyl-2-pentanol	0.93	1.14 (-0.21)	1.03 (-0.10)
32	2,4-Dimethyl-3-pentanol	1.22	1.16 (0.06)	1.16 (0.06)
33	2,2-Dimethyl-3-pentanol	1.15	1.06 (0.09)	1.03 (0.12)
34	3-Heptanol	1.39	1.50 (-0.11)	1.53 (-0.14)
35	4-Heptanol	1.39	1.48 (-0.09)	1.53 (-0.14)
36	1-Octanol	2.35	2.29 (0.06)	2.30 (0.05)
37	2,2,3-Trimethyl-3-pentanol	1.27	1.26 (0.01)	1.31 (-0.04)
38	2-Octanol	2.06	2.15 (-0.09)	2.11 (-0.05)
39	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	2.17	2.01 (0.16)	2.11 (0.06)
40	1-Nonanol	3.00	2.89 (0.11)	2.88 (0.12)
41	2-Nonanol	2.74	2.75 (-0.01)	2.70 (0.04)
42	3-Nonanol	2.66	2.69 (-0.03)	2.70 (-0.04)
43	4-Nonanol	2.59	2.67 (-0.08)	2.70 (-0.11)
44	5-Nonanol	2.49	2.66 (-0.17)	2.70 (-0.21)
45	2,6-Dimethyl-4-heptanol	2.51	2.48 (0.03)	2.33 (0.18)
46	3,5-Dimethyl-4-heptanol	2.30	2.17 (0.13)	2.33 (-0.03)
47	2,2-Diethyl-1-pentanol	2.42	2.10 (0.32)	2.39 (0.03)
48	7-Methyl-1-octanol	2.49	2.75 (-0.26)	2.70 (-0.21)
49	3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol	2.51	2.23 (0.28)	1.90 (0.61)
50	1-Decanol	3.70	3.50 (0.20)	3.47 (0.23)
51	1-Dodecanol	4.64	4.71 (-0.07)	4.64 (0.00)
	Absolute average deviation ^c	-	0.15	0.14

*Deviation in parenthesis. ^aRef. 11. ^bPresent work. ^cAbsolute average deviation = $\sum_{i=1}^{51} |\log S_{exp}(i) - \log S_{calc}(i)| / 51$

Table 3. Water solubilities (log S) for alkanes*

N ⁰	Alkane	-log S _{exp}	-log S _{calc} ^a	-log S _{calc} ^b
1	n-Butane	2.63	2.73 (-0.10)	2.73 (-0.19)
2	2-Methylpropane	2.55	2.66 (-0.11)	2.25 (0.30)
3	n-Pentane	3.27	3.34 (-0.07)	3.31 (-0.04)
4	2-Methylbutane	3.18	3.23 (-0.05)	3.25 (-0.07)
5	3-Methylbutane	3.83	3.79 (0.04)	3.25 (0.58)

Table-3 (contd)

6 Neopentane	3 13	3 08 (0 05)	3 00 (0 13)
7 2,2-Dimethylbutane	3 67	3 61 (0 06)	3 58 (0 09)
8 2,4-Dimethylbutane	4 39	4 28 (0 11)	4 36 (0 03)
9 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane	4 67	4 61 (0 06)	4 68 (-0 01)
10 2,2,5-Trimethylhexane	5 05	5 21 (-0 16)	5 26 (-0 21)
11 Cyclohexane	3 18	3 23(-0 05)	3 13 (0 05)
12 Methylcyclohexane	3 85	3 66 (0 19)	3 66 (0 19)
13 1-cis-2-Dimethylcyclohexane	4 27	4 03 (0 24)	4 18 (0 09)
14 Cycloheptane	3 52	3 70 (-0 18)	3 71 (-0 19)
15 Cyclooctane	4 15	4 24 (-0 09)	4 29 (-0 14)
16 n-Hexane	3 95	3 94 (0 01)	3 89 (0 06)
17 n-Heptane	4 53	4 55 (-0 02)	4 47 (0 06)
18 n-Octane	5 24	5 15 (0 09)	5 05 (0 19)
Absolute average deviation ^d	-	0 09	0 15

*Deviation in parenthesis ^aRef 11 ^bPresent work ^cAbsolute average deviation = $\sum_{i=1}^{18} |\log S_{\text{exp}}(i) - \log S_{\text{inv}}(i)| / 18$

molecular behavior, they make clear the fundamental value of the atom and bond concepts within the framework of the molecular structure paradigm. After all, other more elaborated molecular descriptors always contain some degree of arbitrariness. This is an unavoidable fact due to the strong reduction process when trying to describe a so complex and rather subtle issue as it is the molecular structure concept via a single figure.

Conclusions : We have shown that quite acceptable results for molecular polarizabilities and water solubilities can be obtained through a rather simple set of fitting equations, resorting to the use of atoms and bonds as basic variables. The degree of accuracy is quite satisfactory and the present results compare favorably with previous ones based upon the application of more elaborated molecular descriptors. These findings are in agreement with some former results pointing towards the intrinsic value of the very supporting notions of atoms and chemical bonds as the fundamental primary constituents of molecules.

In order to realize the relative merits of the present approximation scheme, one must take into account the extremely simple calculation procedure to determine the molecular descriptors (just to count atoms and bonds!!), while

in any other case, it is necessary to make use of some sort of algebraic algorithm to compute them.

Present results are in line with other similar findings reported before¹⁰. Naturally, it is not sensible at all to derive more definitive conclusions since we have employed a reduced number of molecular sets, biological activities and physical chemistry properties. However, at present we are studying other molecules and different activities and properties to support the motivating idea of this work. Results will be given elsewhere in future.

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